

SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS, AND GREEN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT (GHRM)

Dr. Krishna Kant Sharma

Department of Labour and Social Welfare; KPS College, Nadwan (Patna), India

Abstract: This paper, aims to establish a better perspective about the Green Human Resources Management (GHRM). The paper seeks to deepen the theoretical and conceptual frameworks through various empirical studies. The paper has sighted various examples and suggested a role for HR leaders. More and more empirical research in the GRHM is the need of the hour. Creation of awareness about the science and needed of environmental betterment would be required in a country like India. The corporate rising in the horizon would certainly cause a trickledown effect in the country for sustained growth and environment management. Becoming integral to the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) at several organizations, GHRM has a future in India and the world.

Key words: Green Human Resources Management (GHRM); Sustainable Business; Business and Environment

INTRODUCTION

People across the world are very much concerned about depleting environmental conditions. Any corporate being a part of the global societies amidst globalization have also realized the concern for the environment. The global development agencies have started taking care about sustainable development and these scenarios Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) has acquired the effects of GRHM could not be restricted to mere the concerned organizations only as it would bound to spread. With more and more awareness about environment GHRM gears for effective environmental management (EM) within organizations. Research in GHRM has emerged as one of the trending areas of HR Management. However, despite the growth in the volume of research in GHRM still several theoretical and conceptual basis have not been properly established. GHRM is now clearly a legitimate field of academic pursuit. It has the potential to offer new insights into the transformation of the forms and means of management, employment, and organizing across the world. (Shuang Ren 2017) There is a strong positive correlation between the evaluation of the impact of individual activities within Green HRM on sustainable company development and their practical implementation. Research demonstrated that the higher the evaluation of the impact of a given activity, the more frequent its implementation in the studied companies. It is necessary to raise awareness and disseminate knowledge concerning the impact Green HRM can have on sustainable development in organizations. (Marciniuk-Kluska 2018). HR leaders being the advocates of organizational culture and policies are critical to inculcate a sense of responsibility in each employee towards a sustainable green human resource management. However, still greater change needs to happen so that employees and organizations take that big leap in ensuring the greening process in all their activities. (Suruchi Pandey 2016).

GREEN HRM AND SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS

Many something green is not the purpose of a green HRM. Even a chemical or plastic could be green in color, however, just on this basis we cannot term them green. Green HRM involves undertaking environment friendly HR initiatives resulting in greater effectiveness, lower cost and better

employee engagement and retention in turn. It helps in the reduction of paper usage and the implementation of green human resource policies such as planning, recruiting, selecting, managing employees and the employee relations. (KarpagamV 2016)

A green HRM transforms an employee into a green employee. The environment friendly, human resource practices and preservation of knowledge capital is considered as green human resource management elements. A green HRM aims to achieve the environmental, organizational goal and as to solve the environmental issues. Under a green HRM all HR policies, practices, and actions are involved with environmental up gradation and protection. An employee can adopt an environment friendly work style or even he or she can give some time to work for betterment of the environment. Such activities may be part of *Corporate Social Responsibility* (CSR).

One of the requirements of a modern day Human Resources Management (HRM) has been the green HRM. However, green HRM has been more or less technology driven and involves a cost. In a country like India there is a need of a type of green HRM based upon cost effective and indigenous technologies. Only maintaining the local ecosystem in which an organization or factory is situated would not work as it now required to adopt a policy and practice to contribute the overall environmental conservation. Many organizations have associated compensation with the green HRM practices of their employees. In a study, it has been found that if green HRM policies are included in performance appraisals and compensation there are some positive outcome. (Farheen Javed 2017).

One of the requirement of turning an organization to a green enterprise it needed to properly check the carbon cycle and reducing to almost null or minimum carbon emission. An organization can adopt the Low Carbon Work System (LCWS), yet it can give high performance. Managers and non-managers required to adopt new behaviors more precisely low carbon behaviors. An employee usually carries values to the workplace imposed by a culture. If sustainable, low-carbon behaviors at individual, team, and material levels are going beyond quaint rhetorical notions of going green, managers collectively have

to develop a “sustainability oriented organizational culture. (Bratton 2015).

A green HRM adopted by a concern can trickle down and people living in the periphery or local surrounding can also adopt a green behavior. The range of green HRM is extended from home and habitation to a work place. Green HRM can play a useful role in business in promoting environment related issues by adopting and following Green HR policies and practices. Green HRM can enhance corporate image and brand. Green HR will play an important role in making the employees aware of and concerned for the preservation of natural resources and contribute in pollution control, waste management and manufacture of eco-friendly products. (Prasad 2013)

Green HRM can be useful and beneficial for the organization also. It can cut short the cost, wastages, and promote the profits. Green HR initiative results higher productivity and build a developmental climate for business. By doing so, organizations would add value to their brand image. The green recruitment, green selection, green induction, green performance appraisal, green compensation and rewards system are powerful tools in making employees more ecofriendly for business sustainability. (Mohanty 2017).

THE SIMPLE SCIENCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION

The science of carbon management is simplified. Carbon emission to the environment can reduce oxygen supply as it gets associated with oxygen to form carbon monoxide, which again adds another molecule of oxygen to produce carbon dioxide. Therefore, more and more emission of carbon can reduce the supply of the oxygen in the environment. The reduced oxygen supply can cause a depletion of the ozone layer as ozone (O₃) is a source of oxygen. Low consumption of oxygen in the atmosphere usually strengthens and sustain the ozone layer. Therefore, world over scientists have suggested low carbon emission as a remedy for sustenance of the ozone layer and not causing it deplete any further. It can cause the rise of temperature. More vaporization of the sea water would cause more rain, floods, and sea level can rise tremendously due to melting of snow at the poles. Glaciers would melt and rising sea levels would disturb the habitations. However, carbon can work as a food supplement for the plants. Therefore, more and more tress would also reduce the carbon level and increase the supply of the oxygen as well. However, even we have also caused a massive deforestation further adding to our miseries. The gene order of the animals and plants could change adversely to cope with the changing weather pattern.

SUGGESTED ACTIVITIES FOR THE COMPANIES TO REDUCE CARBON FOOTPRINTS

Many companies are adopting green practices which help them in reducing carbon footprint to reduce use of paper and many have in fact gone paperless organization. Interviews are organized online or through videoconferencing to cut short the transportation related costs and to reduce the burden due to transportation vehicles. Many companies have introduced e vehicles for its employees.

Some other suggested activities could be for energy saving could be designing the workplace suitable for natural lights and winds. Using energy efficient bulbs and installing a timer to switch off the light, fans, air conditioners, and other office equipment automatically after a definite time. Adopting a proper solid waste disposal system, reducing the use of plastics, promoting the use of biodegradable materials, minimal use of water and recycling of water, using natural products as soaps, detergents, coloring, and using more and more

renewable sources of energy such as solar, wind, and increasing the forest cover. (Shah Ridwan Chowdhury 2017)

For employers and practitioners, it may require to establish the usefulness of linking employee involvement and participation in environmental management programs to improved organizational environmental performance, perhaps via a specific focus on waste management and recycling; for unions and employees, they may help them lobby employers to adopt Green HRM policies and practices that help safeguard and enhance worker health and well-being; and for academics, they may reveal additional data to add an HRM element to the knowledge base on Green Management in general. (Dr. Douglas Renwick 2008)

In a survey of the IT Company, HCL, it has been found that there are numerous green HRM activities being implemented there. Efforts such as a green data center, E Waste Management, Creation of Green Belt, Employee First Council, Community Champions, and Women Connect have been initiated. (Gupta 2015). The focus on improving the operational efficiencies combined with up-gradation of technology have led ITC to be the only company in the world, of its size and diversity, to achieve the milestones of being carbon positive, water positive and achieving almost 100% solid waste recycling. The "Three Leaves" rating awarded by the Centre for Science and Environment, Green Tech Environment Excellence award, "Golden Peacock" award and "Solid Waste Recycling Positive", "Excellent Water Efficient Unit" awards to name a few are testimonies to these efforts and achievement. (Mandip 2012). Some other environmentally-friendly solutions to stay Green has been suggested as Green Printing, Green Manufacturing and Disposal of Staff ID card, Job sharing (sharing a full-time job between two employees), Teleconferencing and virtual interviews, Recycling, Telecommuting, Online Training, Reduce employee carbon footprints by the likes of electronic filling, Green HR involves reducing carbon footprint via less printing of paper, video conferencing and interviews etc.; Energy efficient office spaces, Green Payroll, Car Pooling, Public Transport, Company Transport, Flexi-Work, and e-filing. (Tiwari 2015).

EMPLOYEES SURVEY ON GREEN HRM

According to the 2007 poll on green employment conducted by MonsterTRAK.com⁵, 80% of young professionals were interested in working at a job that contributed positively to the environment and 92% of students and entry-level applicants showed preference to work for a sustainable firm. Another survey by the Carbon Trust⁶ also emphasizes the importance of green policies of a company as an important criterion for prospective employees. The survey findings show that over 75% of 1018 respondents considered active policies of the company to reduce carbon emissions as an important factor while choosing a job. The survey, conducted by the U.K. Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development⁷ (CIPD) reiterates with 49% of respondents taking into account the environmental credentials of the company while deciding to take a job. In fact, the findings of CIPD/KPMG⁸ survey of 1000 respondents show that 47% of HR professionals feel that strong green approach of firms will make employees prefer working for them and also 46% stated that having a green approach would help attract potential employees. (Chugan 2015).

WHAT SHOULD BE DONE?

Linking specific range of Human Resources Management functions and practices, including recruitment, training, development, performance appraisal, and incentives have been regarded as a first major requirement. Recruitment

practices can support effective environmental management by ensuring that new recruits understand an organization's environmental culture and share its environmental values. Graduates and other job applicants pay attention to the environmental management practices and performance of companies and use such information when deciding where to apply. Increasingly, firms are beginning to recognize that gaining a reputation as a Green employer is an effective way to attract new talent. Training Environmental training and establishing a culture in which employees feel they are accountable for environmental outcomes were the most salient HRM practices for achieving environmental goals. Tying incentive pay to the attainment of environmental goals helps focus managers' attention and invigorate efforts aimed at achieving them. Recognitions and financial incentives can be effective in motivating employees to generate eco-initiatives. (Jackson 2011). Empirical studies are needed to enhance the body of knowledge of Green HRM. Major challenges that will be faced by researchers are conceptualization and operationalization of various constructs in the field of Green HRM as valid and reliable instruments need to be developed. (Opatha 2013). Targeting employees who have similar values, motivations and beliefs during the recruitment process, would embed similar minded employees who are more likely to strive to achieve organizational green goals. In addition, organizations that promulgate communication regarding their commitment to and support for sustainability agendas, and employees who consider their actions in regards to meeting environmental compliance requirements, are also more likely to achieve their green objectives. Achieving these green goals is therefore more likely to be successful through the implementation of green HRM processes and activities such as recruitment and selection, training and education, performance appraisals, and rewards and compensation. (Dumont 2015). It is possible to conclude that by understanding and increasing the scope and depth of green HRM practices, organizations can improve their environmental performance in a more sustainable manner than before. The green HRM practices are more powerful tools in making organizations and their operations greener. The green performance, green behaviors, green attitude, and green competencies of human resources can be shaped and reshaped through adaptation of green HRM practices. (A. Anton Arulrajah 2015). The future of green HRM appeared bright. It included green campus and building, green energy, solid waste management, recycling, and paperless works would be the future of the green HRM. (Ahmad1 2015). It has been suggested that new model of the green HRM should include, among others the relationship of assessment-based HR Interventions, environmental management system (EMS), green intellectual capital (GIC) and corporate environmental citizenship (CEC). (Sudin 2011).

SOME EXAMPLES OF GREEN HRM

LG India has launched an LED E60 and E90 series monitor for the Indian market. Its USP is that it consumes 40% less energy than conventional LED monitors. Also, they hardly used halogen or mercury, trying to keep down the use of hazardous materials in their products. *HCL* has recently launched the HCL ME 40 notebooks. These notebooks do not use any polyvinyl chloride (PVC) material or other harmful chemicals and the Bureau of Energy Efficiency already given it a five-star rating. *Haier's* have launched the Eco Life Series. They have semi-automatic and automatic refrigerators and washing machines, split and window air conditioners and a lot more. *Samsung India* has always had a roaring range of LED TV screens and now they have come up with eco- friendly LED

backlight. They use 40% less electricity have also no harmful chemicals like mercury and lead. *Tata Consultancy Services* has a globally recognized Sustainability practice and has already topped the Newsweek's top World's Greenest Company title. It also has a global green score of 80.4% and this has mainly happened due to their initiative of creating technology for agricultural and community benefits. *Oil and Natural Gas Company* is all set to change the way with the invention of green crematoriums, that would serve as a perfect replacement for the funeral pyres that emit so much smoke and uses excess oxygen. *IndusInd Bank* has discouraged the use of paper for the counterfoils in ATMs, and sending electronic messages, it has contributed a lot towards saving paper and reducing deforestation. *ITC* has adopted a Low Carbon Growth Path and a Cleaner Environment Approach and has already introduced ozone treated elemental chlorine free bleaching technology that has improved the lives of millions worldwide. *Wipro*, has not only helped in the creation of technology that helps in saving energy and preventing waste, but its corporate headquarters in Pune is the most eco-friendly building in this sector all over India. *MRF Tyres* have launched the ZSLK series and this is all about creating eco- friendly tubeless tires made from unique silica- based rubber and also offers extra fuel efficiency to those who drive their vehicles. (Ambli 2018).

CONCLUSION

GHRM cannot be implemented mere as a populist measure. It is required to be done with a great application of mind considering the culture, local ecosystem, availability of resources, and skills of the work force. Go green should be inherited part of our culture. It is not an issue of mere sloganeering and eye washing. We cannot simply replace one absurdity with another. The examples of a country or organization cannot be universally implemented. Therefore, it would require empirical studies to have certain theoretical and pragmatic approach in analysis considering protection of the environment at the center.

VITAE

The Author has worked as Divisional Program Manager under the aegis of the *National Rural Health Mission* with the Jharkhand Government. He has remained an ICSSR doctoral and postdoctoral fellows. Taught students at the UG and PG levels subject, such as HR Management and Organizational Behavior.

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